

CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING MUSIC EDUCATION AT THE SPECIALIZED BOARDING SCHOOL “NURLI MASKAN”

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Abstract. *Jas music has a special meaning in the lives of blind people, the role of this art form in the education and upbringing of children born and living with such a fate is incomparable. The fact that this issue is receiving attention at the government level, and the fact that the President has created a legal framework in separate documents, places responsibility on teaching staff. Although there is some experience at the world level, there is a lack of music education for the blind in our country's education, in particular, the teaching of Braille notation. In most cases, lessons are based on auditory learning.*

This article consists of ten points based on the priority, role and significance of music for teachers and educators working in specialized boarding schools "Nurli Maskan" and music teachers in teaching blind and visually impaired children. Based on a special decision of the President of our country, the uniqueness of music education in these schools, the content of the activities of music teachers and other aspects that should be paid attention to are highlighted. It is recommended to use music and singing not only in music lessons, but also in other subjects and academic subjects taught in these schools in an integrated manner.

Keywords: *music, pedagogy, Nurli Maskan schools, Braille, education, education of the blind, integration.*

Introduction: Music is a world of joy and happiness, impressions for children. Listening to music, singing, playing outdoor games to tunes and dancing are some of the favorite activities of children. In the process of learning to play musical instruments, they develop good feelings. Music is the most effective source of aesthetic education and moral development of children. The role of music is especially great in the education of blind and visually impaired children. Typically, this category of children is naturally interested in literature and art, especially music. After all, music is a dear companion, bringing peace of joy and comfort to their lonely hearts, and an integral part of their lives. In recent years, in our country, based on the principle “For Human Dignity,” there have been providing assistance to people with disabilities, improving the system of their comprehensive support, including increasing the activity and place of blind and visually impaired children in society, measures are being taken for strengthen it. To ensure systematization and consistency of reforms in this direction, further improvement of the conditions created for the education of blind and visually impaired children, their preparation for independent life, assistance and support for their adaptation in society, a certain scope of activities are carried out regarding the support.

Materials and methodology of the study. Resolution PR-209 dated April 18, 2022 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M.Mirziyayev “On measures to improve the quality of education in specialized boarding schools for blind and visually impaired children and further improve their activities” [1] become of great importance in systematizing and improving the education of children with educational needs. By decision of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and

the Ministry of Public Education, specialized boarding schools for blind and visually impaired children were attached to the Ministry of Internal Affairs and were called specialized boarding schools such as “Nurli Maskan” school.

In this document, the Ministry of Internal Affairs assigned officials to the schools named after Nurli Maskan:

provide quality education and upbringing, improve their living conditions, as well as meaningfully organize students’ free time and develop their intellectual, physical and creative abilities;

based on the physical capabilities of students, to educate them into healthy, intellectually mature people, to shape their worldview, to interest and attract them to sports;

the task of constantly providing assistance in organizing cultural and educational events that shape the patriotic feelings of students is envisaged.

According to a special article and the relevant paragraphs of this decision, textbooks and teaching aids in Braille, fiction and children's literature, printed and audio books related to various specialties and areas of education for blind and visually impaired students have sufficient material and technical base and experience in this direction based on state orders. Accompanying tasks, such as publication in existing printing houses and distribution of “Nurli Maskan” to schools in accordance with their needs, are negotiated separately; it was noted that natural science Olympiads will be organized among blind and visually impaired graduates on a separate regional and republican scale; It has also been determined to carry out practical work on organizing courses in foreign languages, information technologies, vocational training and entrepreneurship for students of Nurli Maskan schools. In addition, the solution includes many other necessary measures, namely: rehabilitation and rehabilitation of blind and visually impaired children, involving them in full education, inclusive education of persons with special educational needs, creating the necessary conditions for learning, creating training and production enterprises for them in the school building, create network clubs for Barkamol Avlod children's schools based on the needs and capabilities of their students, organize Paralympic sports clubs and attract qualified trainers for sports (judo, football, athletics), modern renovation and equipment of educational buildings. The decision also provides for the development of art (music) in the schools of Nurli Maskan, the attachment of students to music and art schools in the regions in order to realize their talents in art, girls “Doyrachilar”, “Dutorchi”, Folklore groups are also being created. Of course, the scientific basis and methodological approaches to this determine the effectiveness of teachers’ work. For this purpose, there is some experience in children's pedagogy in the world and partly in our country.

Literature review. French scientist and educator Valentin Gahuy (1745-1822) focused his entire career on music education. He teaches students to play instruments such as harpsichord, clavecord, piano and sing in a choir. “He always emphasized the vital importance of reading, saying: “The mind of a blind man who has not received an education will consist only of abstract and chaotic ideas” [3. 16.].

For the first time, the opinion about the need to create a book for the blind was expressed by V. Gayuy. Although his economic situation in this regard is difficult, he builds a special printing house at the school and prints many books in the “uncial” script he invented. For example, among them are the brochures “On the Education of Blind Children”, “A Brief Grammar of the French Language”, “A Grammar of the Latin Language”. Blind people used these books until six-dot

Braille was invented. Due to this, not only there was the systematic training of visually impaired people established, but also views were formed on them as full members of society, in need of education and social adaptation, just like healthy people.

Louis Braille (1809-1852), another French scientist and teacher, the founder of Braille, also used music effectively in his work. At the same time, L. Braille was also a good musicologist. "Since he knew music theory very well, he also created a system of Braille signs and displayed many musical symbols in a 6-point system" [6. 23.]. This discovery of the scientist led blind people into the world of music and brought positive changes to their lives.

At present time many scientists are effectively searching in the field of typhoid pedagogy. "Yu.B. Ryabkin - congenital and acquired forms of color discrimination, professor of the Leningrad Pedagogical Institute named after A.I. Gersen, B.I. Kovalenko made a great contribution to the development of the science of pedagogy and the development of methods for teaching the blind general subjects. M.I. Zemsova, A.I. Litvak, V. Fromm, J. Yasensky studied the features of the development of thinking depending on the degree of visual impairment. In 2005, one of the domestic scientists of Uzbekistan, Sh. Khalilova, conducted a study on the topic "Peculiarities of thinking of visually impaired children," O. Rustamov conducted research on the formation of mathematical concepts in visually impaired children [4. 24]. However, there is not enough scientific literature for the blind in the field of music. This puts on the agenda the need to conduct scientific and methodological research on the creation of music education in specialized boarding schools "Nurli Maskan" .

Discussion and results: It is known that the first musical tone in raising a child begins with the mother. "Alla calms and calms children, children who fall asleep listening to "Alla" also say "Alla" to their dolls. Relaxing music doesn't have to be a song. In all times and peoples, mothers sang to their babies in a quiet voice, repeating two- and three-note melodies. Every culture has simple songs about love and holidays that children can memorize to help them express their feelings." 2.].

As children grow and develop their minds, they are introduced to other genres of music. For example, in preschool education, the teacher uses melodies characteristic of a marching rhythm. It gives the child a feeling of pride, enthusiasm, enthusiasm and freshness. However, background music should be treated with caution. In most cases, when music is played, it is the center of children's attention, distracting them from their main activities, and even music that is too loud can have a negative impact on their hearing and psyche.

Music can only be a beneficial factor if people maintain a daily routine. Congratulatory and holiday songs performed in a group bring children endless joy and excitement. Songs are a great way to relax children during recess.

The role of music in the education of blind children is invaluable. When children of this type are taught, when they first come to the first school, they feel weak and weak, they feel that they cannot complete any task, the music teacher and at the same time other teachers or the lesson preparer and the group teacher (even if the subject not musical)) if they can listen to music for several minutes, they partially achieve the activation of visually impaired children in classes and groups. Because blind children show their talent more easily in this regard. Moreover. Musical activity builds a child's strong will, patience and perseverance, and increases self-confidence.

In addition, teachers and educators working with children with visual impairments should prioritize the pedagogical and psychological approach to them in all forms of education. To

achieve this, the first step in this regard is to determine the children's vision level. That is, they will have to find out at what age blind children lost their sight, how far the visually impaired child can see and the type of disease according to the doctor's conclusion about his health.

“Two multidirectional processes in typhlopsychology - a relatively deep differentiation of visually impaired people: total blindness; he has no eye that senses light; blind with residual vision; visually impaired; visually impaired. These trends influence the psychological characteristics of visually impaired children, determine the degree and strength of the impact of various forms of visual pathology on the mental development of children, as well as the possibility of their compensation in the course of individual work and special correctional training.” 4.21.]

At Nurli Maskan schools, children with different levels of vision are taught together in the same class. Typically, visually impaired children perceive the world around them and various objects and events in it mainly through hearing and intuition. Depending on the level of vision or blindness of children, their perception of the environment is different, so the teacher takes into account the level of vision of students and approaches them individually, using a unique pedagogical method. This is especially evident in practical classes: musical culture, labor, physical education, fine arts (typhlography). In addition, it is useful if teachers and educators have modeling skills. Because it is very convenient to create the necessary exhibitions using plastic objects for blind children to form an idea of the shape of celestial bodies, natural landscapes, as well as objects that are very large in shape. “An important achievement common to all children is the creation of an image when working with plastic materials. The creation of a primary image is a feature of all artistic activity, including sculpting” [2.151]. Modeling is the most effective way to teach blind children.

While working with blind and visually impaired students, a music culture teacher should implement a shoe-pedagogical approach, adhering to the following recommendations:

1. Students entering the room line up to the sound of marches and other such exciting melodies; in this case, the student's interest and mood in the lesson will rise to an excellent level, and other thoughts will be forgotten. To ensure that students can walk around in a music room, desks should be spaced evenly and the teacher should ensure there are no undue obstructions.

2. Using musical tones as a response while greeting students; these tones consist of successive sounds in the form of a scale, which ensures that students are mentally prepared for the lesson.

3. The teacher should briefly tell students about political, cultural news, news of the day or show it on the screen in the form of a video, picture and explain it in the child's language; The displayed video and image should be enlarged if necessary. Blind children need to describe an object, an object, an event, if it exists, the shape and state of the relief, and in situations where this is not possible, it is necessary to create in them, like other students, an understanding as much as possible.

4. Tuning the voice by singing gamma exercises to the accompaniment of a piano or other national instruments; While singing, it is necessary to teach visually impaired students how to breathe correctly, keep their bodies upright, open their mouths beautifully, and produce high-quality sound.

5. Teaching a new topic according to the work plan:

a) if the topic is a lecture, the teacher gives an understanding of the topic with the help of a presentation, picture, or exhibition prepared on it. The displayed video and image should be enlarged if necessary. Blind children are given understanding as above;

b) if the new subject is a song, then it will be possible to teach everyone using the same method. Because writing the words of a song is written, and singing is characteristic of the oral method;

c) if the subject of the lesson is listening to music, students are taught the rules of listening to music, i.e. harmony of melody and rhythm, tempo, what instruments are involved in performing the melody; he is taught to focus on logical aspects, such as what scene you can imagine when you hear a melody.

6. Combining topics. Reviewing the topics covered one at a time is very useful for students. This activity is carried out in the form of tests and questions, in the form of the game “Think, Seek, Find”, by singing a song and performing dance movements to it (rhythmic movements with blind students).

7. According to the plan of work in musical culture lessons, blind students should be taught Braille in accordance with their reading and music literacy (the practice of teaching Braille to read and write has not developed to date).

8. Student assessment, moral stimulation. The assessment process is the most enjoyable moment for the student, and the memorable and solemn organization of this part of the lesson depends on pedagogical skill. For example, cheer on children who received 5 points with loud music, and applaud with firecrackers for children who received 4 points. To remember moments of spiritual encouragement for students, presenting the most active student with a label, flag, star and other small gifts reflecting the level of “best participation in the lesson”, etc. When making them, the teacher uses thick paper (gaffri, cardboard) or bright and shiny, colored smooth paper that is more suitable for blind and visually impaired students.

9. Giving homework. Typically, home assignments in musical culture classes consist of memorizing or consolidating learned song lyrics, reading the lives and works of certain composers and composers. Constantly this kind of task tired the student. According to the principle of intersubjectivity, if students are given tasks that encourage them to work on themselves and search, for example, drawing pictures related to the topic being studied, making models, guessing riddles about these objects, proverbs, poems, songs, then together with music, students study fine arts, labor, strengthen their knowledge and skills in subjects such as literature.

10. Finishing the lesson. It's even better if this process is musical, just like the greeting. When the teacher says goodbye to the students and ends the lesson with warm words such as: “I will wait for you until the next lesson”, “I will miss you”, “Be healthy always”, “Take care of yourself”, it will make the students look forward to the next one lesson and do your homework well.

Conclusions and proposals. It should be mentioned that if the above recommendations are applied to the activities of teachers and music teachers involved in teaching children with visual impairments, these activities will be effective during their lessons. Teachers and educators working with blind and visually impaired children must regularly work on themselves, develop their knowledge and skills, and keep abreast of innovations introduced specifically for the blind. Teachers must be dedicated to their profession, enthusiastic and fair to students. In addition, other employees working at Nurli Maskan specialized boarding schools must know how to teach blind

children, understand their walking abilities, help them move independently around the school grounds and remove obstacles on the road. After all, the Head of our state entrusts to the bright future and education of the disabled children in the Republic.

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